

“LISTENING” AS EXEMPLIFIED BY VALLUVAR: AN ANALYSIS

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The Tamil Lexicon (vol. 1 and 2: 1982) explains that the word “kelvi” (question/hearing) has various meanings including inquiry, questioning, asking about textual content, education, sound, Vedas, text, word, ear, investigation, musical note, and harp. Not every one gets the opportunity to obtain knowledge through formal education owing to lack of resources, certain life situations, or miscellaneous indispensable reasons. Yet, it is undeniable that learning is possible through listening and observation. Therefore, Tamils have emphasised “hearing/listening” as one of the sources of knowledge.

References to “kelvi” are found throughout Tamil literature since the Sangam period. These references mainly indicate listening to textual content which are mainly religious and didactic in nature. Everything heard by the ear constitutes “kelvi.” Hence, “kelvi” can be considered as a doorway to gain all types of knowledge.

Parimelazhagar states that “kelvi” refers to listening to what those who have studied texts have to say. Manakkudavar believes that those who cannot study all texts should listen to those who have studied them. This is referred to as “wealth of form” and is considered the greatest among all types of wealth. Thiruvalluvar emphasises in his couplets that one should listen attentively to what others say rather than constantly speaking. At the same time, we should note that other texts have not given as much prominence or extensive discussion to “kelvi” as Thiruvalluvar did. This article explores the various contexts in which listening enriches one’s self and materialistic life as well.

The Excellence of Hearing/Listening

Thiruvalluvar has described the excellence of listening and the benefits of hearing in ten couplets in the 42nd chapter titled “kelvi.” Just as he praises education, Valluvar also praises the act of listening. He says:

**Among all wealth, the wealth of hearing is the finest wealth;
that wealth is the foremost among all other forms of wealth. (411)**

The wealth of knowledge gained through hearing (through the ears) is superior to all other forms of wealth.

Thirikadugam, one of the eighteen minor didactic works that appeared after Thiruvalluvar, elaborately explains the primary aspects of listening in verses 31 and 63. It explains that there are six types of wealth:

1. Wealth of education
2. Wealth of listening/hearing
3. Wealth of grace
4. Material wealth
5. Wealth of knowledge
6. Wealth of children

The wealth acquired through the ears in the form of enriching thoughts is considered the foremost among these types.

Ways to Acquire the Wealth of Listening

Regarding the wealth of listening, Viswanathan remarks as follows:

There are two ways to acquire the wealth of listening/hearing. One is to learn by actively listening. The other is to learn without intentional listening. “Speaking without saying” means conveying through implications. “Thinking without consciously thinking” means remembering without forgetting, rather than forgetting and then remembering. “Going without thinking about going” means traveling without wondering where one is going. “Hearing without asking” means listening to what others say voluntarily without us asking them.

Places where one can hear without asking include speech platforms, music halls, theatres, cinemas, railway stations, riverbanks, pond banks, water taps, and so on. Those who naturally have the opportunity to hear without asking are vehicle drivers. Passengers in horse carriages, rickshaws, and motor vehicles often speak as if the driver doesn’t exist, thinking they

are alone, and discuss matters they shouldn’t be talking about. There is no news in town that drivers don’t know! This is why these drivers appear more talented than others. In England, a driver became an excellent writer and amassed great wealth. Do you know the name of the first book he published? It was “What Fell Into My Ears.” As far as he was concerned, listening became his wealth. (14–15)

Only those who have gained wisdom by attentively listening and have become cultured will have the ability to speak with humility; others do not possess this quality. Recognising this importance, Naladiyar, which came after Thirukkural, also strongly emphasises this point. Those who are free from jealousy speak about the path of virtue, but those who lack goodness will not listen even if they lend their ears—just as a scavenging dog that gnaws on hides cannot appreciate the quality of rice cooked in milk (Naladiyar 33)

In the Sangam literature Purananuru, Pothiyar, while praising King Kopperuncholan, says:

He was renowned for giving to singers; He was full of great affection for dancers; He was like a refined sceptre praised by the virtuous; He was of pleasant friendship praised by the capable; He had the grace of women and the valour of men; He was a refuge for the elevated ones with flawless learning; Without saying he was merely like these, that worthy king...” (Puram: 221:1–7)

The poet indicates that Kopperuncholan stood as a sanctuary for noble people with flawless hearing/learning. The “kelvi” mentioned here refers to the knowledge gained by listening to those who have studied and understood sacred, philosophical and didactic texts.

This concept of listening to textual knowledge can be categorised into two types:

7. Listening by those who have already studied texts
8. Listening by those who have not studied texts

Valluvar Says

Even if one has not studied, one should listen; that will be

A support against faltering, like a staff. (414)

He says that even if one has not properly studied good texts, one should eagerly listen to others' discourses. That will serve as a supporting staff that helps one walk without stumbling.

Listen to good things, however small; even those

Will bring greatness that is complete. (416)

Those who have meticulously acquired learning

Will not speak foolishness even if they understand incorrectly. (417)

These couplets emphasise that even if one has studied something, by listening to another scholar's explanation or perspective on the same subject, one can discern many subtle ideas that were not apparent to them.

Learning good things among many things, and

Living a householder's life without hindrance by sharing food with others, and Creating wealth efficiently through hard work—these three

Are foremost among all aspects of listening. (Thirikadugam 31)

Sharing the company of learned people and learning good things through their ideas, living a life that involves contributing while maintaining one's own dignity, and creating new wealth through hard work—these are considered the foremost among the wealth of listening, according to Thirikadugam. Similarly, Aathichudi

states: "Strive to listen" (Aathichudi 39), that is, whenever there is an opportunity, one should attentively listen to what good people say.

The Loss of Not Listening

Valluvar also speaks about the cost of not listening.

Ears that are not pierced by learning through listening

Would be better off pierced (for ornaments), even if they can hear. (418)

When there is no food for the ear,

A little may be given to the stomach as well. (412)

For people who know only the taste perceived by the mouth,

And not the taste perceived by the ear, what does it matter whether they live or die? (420)

Valluvar severely criticises those who do not gain through listening. This makes clear that even if one cannot learn through texts, listening to the learned will be highly beneficial. Such knowledge gained through listening will stand by us like a gushing spring in times of weakness, flowing abundantly as our support.

The proverb "Listening is better than reading" suggests that learning by hearing is superior to learning from texts. The Nannul sutra places emphasis on listening as a precursor to learning. In our old learning methods, there was a practice called "reciting lessons." A student should listen and learn the lessons taught by a qualified teacher. Since "kelvi" includes both hearing and asking questions, learning through discussion, in a question-and-answer format, has also been considered superior. A line from Naladiyar goes thus: "Those who recite orally and understand the nuances..." (312). Nannul says about listening:

Becoming as eager as one who drinks, Being composed like a painted statue,

With ears as the entrance and the mind as the container,

Storing what is heard without losing anything,

Departing when told to leave, say the scholars. (40; italics added)

The nature of studying texts is to understand usage,

To preserve the lesson and remember what was heard,

To listen properly to what the teacher imparts,

To practice with those who have such dignity,

To ask questions and resolve doubts—

If these are taken as duties, ignorance will be greatly overcome. (41; italics added)

From this, it is understood that rather than learning on one's own, it is better to learn by properly listening to lessons from a suitable teacher. Grammars were once taught orally. Over time, they were standardised and taught as grammatical rules.

They will not be like frogs in a well

That think there is nothing sweet elsewhere—

Those who diligently study calculations all day without weariness;

Listening is better than learning (by oneself). (Pazhamozhi Nanuru 143)

This indicates that listening to lessons from the learned rather than reading and learning texts by oneself was considered superior.

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